

Physico-Chemical Studies of Emulsions with Surfactants as Emulsifying Agents : Part I.

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Oil-in-water emulsions with water and kerosene oil as external and internal phases and sodium dioctyl sulphosuccinate (anionic surfactant), cetyl pyridinium bromide (cationic surfactant) and poly-oxyethylene sorbitan monostearate (non-ionic surfactant) as emulsifying agents have been prepared. Properties like emulsion type, specific gravity, interfacial tension, viscosity, conductivity, pH and particle size of these emulsions have been measured. Low interfacial tension and specific gravity, high viscosity, conductivity and particle size favour emulsification and increase stability of emulsions.

Emulsions of different types have been prepared by taking two immiscible liquids as internal and external phases and surface-active materials¹⁻⁴, naturally-occurring substances^{5,6} and finely-divided solids^{7,8} as emulsifying agents. Various papers and patents employing electrolytes^{9,10}, colloids¹¹, resin soaps¹², water soluble gums^{13,14}, organic compounds^{15,16}, sulphonic acids and sulphonated oils¹⁷ etc. as emulsifying agents have been cited in the literature.

Another important aspect of the chemistry of emulsions which has not been thoroughly investigated is the use of surfactants and their mixtures, taking binary mixtures like anionic + cationic, cationic + nonionic and nonionic + anionic surfactants and tertiary mixtures like anionic + cationic + nonionic surfactants for making emulsions. In the present investigation attempts are being made to carry out the physico-chemical studies on the preparation.

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and properties of emulsions by taking single surfactants (anionic, cationic and nonionic) as emulsifying agents and water and kerosene oil (K.O.) as continuous and disperse phases. Work on binary and tertiary mixtures of surfactants is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : Sodium di-octyl sulphosuccinate (Manoxol OT-anionic surfactant), cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB-cationic surfactant) were B.D.H. England products and Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monostearate (Tween 60-nonionic surfactant) was obtained from M/s. Koch-Light Laboratories Ltd., London. In all the experiments double distilled K.O. (b.p. 205° and sp. gr. .7948925 at 30°) and double distilled water (*pH* 6.2 and conductivity $.85 \times 10^{-6}$ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) were used.

Preparation of Emulsions : Emulsions were prepared under following conditions by Agent-in-water method¹⁸.

- a) Different concentrations of water and K.O. and fixed concentration of emulsifying agent.
- b) Different concentrations of emulsifying agent and fixed ratio of water and K.O.

To the aqueous solution of emulsifying agent, K.O. was added slowly with constant stirring. The emulsion thus made was homogenized by considerable agitation with the help of Braun Emulsifier.

Properties of Emulsions . Emulsion type (O/W or W/O) was determined by the Dye solubility method¹⁹. Calcomine Blue (soluble in water and insoluble in K.O.) and Savinyl Green (soluble in K.O. and insoluble in water) were added to two separate parts of each emulsion and the mixture gently agitated. It was observed that in every case, the part in which Calcomine Blue was added, turned blue and the other part remained milky white. Thus the water constituted the continuous phase and K.O. the disperse phase and all the emulsions were O/W type.

Particle size was determined by taking a photomicrograph of the microscopic slide of the emulsion with the help of Carl Zeiss Jena Microscope fitted with attachment camera using 15×ocular and 40×objective. After the photograph was taken, a stage micrometer with a ruling 1 mm. long and divided into 100 equal parts was placed on the microscope stage and all camera and microscope adjustments were made exactly as they were when the picture was taken. With the lines of the stage micrometer carefully focussed on the ground glass of the camera, the image was measured with an ordinary millimeter scale. The magnification was calculated by the following formula.²⁰

$$\text{Magnification} = \frac{\text{Distance in the image field}}{\text{Equivalent distance in the object field}}$$

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Viscosity, specific gravity and interfacial tension were determined at 30° by the usual Ostwald viscometer, pycnometer and drop weight methods respectively. pH and conductivity were measured at 20° by Beckman pH meter and conductance meter with "magic-eye".

The results are summarised in Tables I-VI.

TABLE I

Emulsions stabilized by Anionic surfactant

Emulsion Type : O/W; Manoxol OT = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.

Emulsion No.	Water (ml.).	O/W Ratio	pH at 20°C	Conductivity		Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity at 30°C	Viscosity at 30°C ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Interfacial Tension at 30°C (dynes/cm)
				at 20°C ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)					
1.	10	1 : 1	7.25	10.5	9-10	.8867814	38.01933	45.59923	
2.	20	1 : 2	7.20	8.5	8-9	.9132573	15.90686	49.57111	
3.	30	1 : 3	7.15	6.8	7-8	.9500906	9.75908	53.55208	
4.	40	1 : 4	7.10	5.3	6-7	.9660150	9.27626	56.63227	
5.	50	1 : 5	7.10	4.0	5-6	.9714202	9.11100	58.11080	
6.	60	1 : 6	7.05	3.25	4-5	.9760163	8.93637	59.60253	
7.	70	1 : 7	7.05	2.95	3-4	.9770520	8.72734	60.93304	
8.	80	1 : 8	7.00	2.7	3-4	.9784114	8.52122	62.34979	
9.	90	1 : 9	7.00	2.5	2-3	.9799326	8.31554	63.83002	
10.	100	1 : 10	7.00	2.3	2-3	.9819070	8.11321	65.41408	

TABLE II

Emulsion Type : O/W; O/W ratio = 1 : 3; K.O. = 30 ml.

Emulsion No.	Manoxol OT (g.)	pH at 20°C	Conductivity		Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity at 30°C	Viscosity at 30°C ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Interfacial Tension at 30°C (dynes/cm.)
			at 20°C ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)					
11.	.01	6.50	0.2	1-2	.9516442	9.35040	63.39531	
12.	.02	6.55	0.7	1-2	.9513529	9.38993	61.96719	
13.	.03	6.60	1.3	2-3	.9510616	9.42946	60.60092	
14.	.04	6.70	2.0	3-4	.9508026	9.49110	59.29885	
15.	.05	6.80	2.8	4-5	.9505761	9.55184	58.04514	
16.	.07	6.90	3.8	5-6	.9503819	9.61347	56.84859	
17.	.10	7.00	5.1	6-7	.9502200	9.67623	55.70598	
18.	.15	7.15	6.8	7-8	.9500906	9.75908	53.55208	
19.	.20	7.35	8.8	8-9	.9499611	9.86404	44.90980	
20.	.25	7.55	11.0	9-10	.9498333	9.96900	37.62323	
21.	.30	7.80	13.4	10-11	.9497993	10.07396	31.99811	
22.	.40	8.10	16.0	11-12	.9497669	10.18004	26.01713	
23.	.50	8.40	19.0	12-13	.9497345	10.28611	21.74860	

TABLE III

Emulsions stabilized by Cationic surfactant

Emulsion Type : O/W; CPB = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.

Emulsion No.	Water (ml.)	O/W Ratio	pH at 20°C	Conductivity		Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity at 30°C	Viscosity at 30°C ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Interfacial Tension at 30°C (dynes/cm)
				at 20°C ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)					
1.	10	1 : 1	6.00	12.0		8-9	.8973329	33.06353	48.70785
2.	20	1 : 2	6.20	9.0		7-8	.9326450	11.66302	52.57128
3.	30	1 : 3	6.40	6.1		6-7	.9497993	9.54391	55.67667
4.	40	1 : 4	6.60	4.1		5-6	.9600271	9.00426	57.42899
5.	50	1 : 5	6.70	3.0		4-5	.9662739	8.84664	59.00396
6.	60	1 : 6	6.80	2.8		3-4	.9714849	8.67732	60.58363
7.	70	1 : 7	6.85	2.7		2-3	.9752718	8.60237	62.14307
8.	80	1 : 8	6.90	2.6		2-3	.9782819	8.51961	63.71922
9.	90	1 : 9	6.95	2.55		1-2	.9814862	8.43790	65.38066
10.	100	1 : 10	7.00	2.5		1-2	.9826191	8.33850	66.98290

TABLE IV

Emulsion Type : O/W; O/W Ratio = 1 : 3; K.O. = 30 ml.

Emulsion No.	CPB (g.)	pH at 20°C	Conductivity		Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity at 30°C	Viscosity at 30°C ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Interfacial Tension at 30°C (dynes/cm.)
			at 20°C ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)					
11.	.01	6.85	1.5		1-2	.9529712	8.29926	64.95827
12.	.02	6.80	1.6		1-2	.9524210	8.50759	63.44866
13.	.03	6.75	1.8		1-2	.9519031	8.71571	62.00618
14.	.04	6.70	2.1		2-3	.9514176	8.92359	60.62642
15.	.05	6.65	2.6		3-4	.9509645	9.13126	59.30530
16.	.07	6.60	3.5		4-5	.9505437	9.33968	58.04514
17.	.10	6.50	4.6		5-6	.9501553	9.44184	56.83658
18.	.15	6.40	6.1		6-7	.9497993	9.54391	55.67667
19.	.20	6.20	8.0		7-8	.9494756	9.60450	52.50855
20.	.25	6.00	10.0		8-9	.9492167	9.66607	47.15867
21.	.30	5.80	12.1		9-10	.9490225	9.74881	40.31561
22.	.40	5.60	14.3		10-11	.9488930	9.85269	34.33551
23.	.50	5.30	16.5		11-12	.9488283	9.95864	29.27554

TABLE V

Emulsions stabilized by Nonionic surfactant

Emulsion Type : O/W; Tween 60 = .05 g.; K.O. = 10 ml.; pH at 20° = 6.8

Emulsion No.	Water (ml.)	O/W Ratio	Conductivity		Specific Gravity at 30°C	Viscosity at 30°C ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Interfacial Tension at 30°C (dynes/cm.)
			at 20°C ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	Particle size (μ)			
1.	10	1 : 1	1.4	7-8	.8942905	19.96927	30.83703
2.	20	1 : 2	1.45	6-7	.9298614	11.00507	32.25430
3.	30	1 : 3	1.5	5-6	.9490225	9.96074	33.11639
4.	40	1 : 4	1.6	4-5	.9587001	9.42026	33.57484
5.	50	1 : 5	1.7	3-4	.9644614	9.04553	33.85536
6.	60	1 : 6	1.9	2-3	.9696724	8.66124	34.07844
7.	70	1 : 7	2.2	2-3	.9741714	8.48390	34.27776
8.	80	1 : 8	2.6	1-2	.9780877	8.40866	34.45657
9.	90	1 : 9	3.0	1-2	.9813568	8.32746	34.61427
10.	100	1 : 10	3.5	1-2	.9841403	8.24134	34.75497

TABLE VI

Emulsion Type : O/W; O/W ratio = 1 : 3; pH at 20° = 6.8; K.O. = 30 ml.

Emulsion No.	Tween 60 (g.)	Conductivity		Particle size (μ)	Specific Gravity at 30°C	Viscosity at 30°C ($\times 10^{-3}$ poises)	Interfacial Tension at 30°C (dynes/cm.)
		at 20°C ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)					
11.	.01	1.25		1-2	.9518384	8.92735	47.28794
12.	.02	1.25		1-2	.9512558	9.34656	44.25759
13.	.03	1.25		2-3	.9507379	9.55396	41.59335
14.	.04	1.25		2-3	.9502848	9.65503	39.22928
15.	.05	1.25		3-4	.9498964	9.75702	37.12169
16.	.07	1.3		3-4	.9495727	9.83876	35.68243
17.	.10	1.4		4-5	.9492814	8.89924	34.35016
18.	.15	1.5		5-6	.9490225	9.96074	33.11639
19.	.20	1.6		6-7	.9487959	9.97877	31.96411
20.	.25	1.7		7-8	.9486017	9.99891	30.89565
21.	.30	1.9		8-9	.9484399	10.01798	30.21736
22.	.40	2.3		9-10	.9483104	10.03810	29.57130
23.	.50	2.7		10-11	.9482133	10.05822	29.25707

DISCUSSION

During the preparation of emulsions, it was observed that when the quantity of K.O. was more than that of water, thick, viscous and concentrated emulsions were obtained which

may be due to the fact that phenomenon of creaming occurred and rate of creaming increased with the increase in concentration of oil. Emulsions with minimum water content and/or maximum emulsifying agent concentration were found to be most stable.

From the tables, it may be seen that interfacial tension decreases with a decrease in the concentration of continuous phase (water) or an increase in the concentration of emulsifying agent and the lower the interfacial tension of emulsions, the greater the stability. Interfacial tension has been emphasized as a factor in forming emulsions as well as in maintaining stability. The emulsifying agent reduces the interfacial tension between the two phases, it decreases the free surface energy of the emulsion formed and tends to produce a stable emulsion. Thus there is a relationship between interfacial tension and emulsifier efficiency of surfactant *i.e.*, as the interfacial tension increases, the emulsifying power decreases. Our results are in agreement with those of previous workers²¹.

From the data, it is clear that viscosity increases as the concentration of continuous phase decreases or concentration of emulsifying agent increases and greater the viscosity, the greater is the stability of emulsions. Viscosity aids the emulsification by decreasing the mobility of the droplets constituting the disperse phase there by retarding their approach and coalescence. Thus by virtue of the hindrance offered to the coalescence of the dispersed globules, the emulsion system becomes permanent. Similar results have been obtained by Neogy and Ghosh²² with water-in-benzene emulsions stabilized by magnesium oleate.

In determining particle size, it was observed that even in a single emulsion, the droplet diameters were not uniform. In each emulsion, droplets of maximum diameters were selected and particle size determined. As may be seen from the results, particle size increases with the decrease in concentration of external phase (water) or increase in concentration of surfactant. Thus droplet-size distribution with sharply defined maximum diameter droplets *i.e.*, a coarser emulsion represents a situation of maximum stability.

In emulsions, stabilized by anionic and cationic surfactants, the greater the W/O ratio, the lower is the conductivity while with non-ionic surfactant the reverse is the case. Our results with Tween 60, coincide with these of Ben' Kovskii²³ with petroleum emulsions. There is an increase in conductivity, with the increase in concentration of each type of emulsifying agent.

In case of anionic surfactant, *pH* decreases with increase in concentration of external phase and with increase in concentration of surfactant the tendency of emulsion to become alkaline from acidic increases. With cationic surfactant, *pH* value increases with increase in concentration of water and decreases with increase in concentration of emulsifying agent. While in case of non-ionic surfactant there is no effect of external phase or emulsifying agent on *pH* value and the emulsion remains acidic.

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Specific gravity of emulsions increases with increase in W/O ratio and decreases with increase in surfactant concentration.

It may be concluded that most stable emulsions are formed with lowest interfacial tension, highest viscosity, maximum droplet diameter, highest conductivity and lowest specific gravity values.

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